

The Book of Deuteronomy

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Entry tags: Canonical texts, Christianity, Hebrew Bible, Religious Group, Rewriting/Rewritten Bible, Greek, Israelite Religion, Text, Canaanite Religions, Language, Jewish Traditions, Judeans and Israelites

The book of Deuteronomy the fifth book of the Hebrew Bible, positioned as the final book of the Pentateuch (Genesis – Deuteronomy), and the first book of the Deuteronomistic History (Joshua – Kings). The book holds a unique position between these two “collections” and many scholars argue it serves as a bridge between the pre-history of Israel in the Pentateuch and the history of Israel’s monarchy as described in Joshua-Kings. In the Jewish tradition, the book is titled “devārīm” or “words,” named after the first few words of the book. In the Christian tradition, the title “Deuteronomy” comes from the Greek Septuagint and means “second law” or “repetition,” as Deuteronomy consists a second iteration of the law previously given in the Covenant Code (Exodus 20-23). The book of Deuteronomy is structured as several speeches given by Moses to the Israelite community as they leave Egypt and prepare to enter the promised land. The core of the book is chapters 12-26 which contain the core content of the “second law.” Michael Coogan suggests that this core is surrounded by a dual introduction (ch. 1-4 and 5-11), two additional speeches (ch. 27-30), a conclusion (ch. 34), and some supplementary poetry (ch. 32:1-44), narrative (ch. 31; 32:45-52), and blessings (ch. 33). Given the book’s composite nature, scholars agree it was likely composed through several stages of editorial activity over a long period of time. While the dates of these layers are largely unknown, editorial activity likely spanned from as early as the 8th century BCE through the early Persian Period. Several scholars have noted similarities between the book of Deuteronomy and Mesopotamian, Hittite, and Aramaic treaty traditions and law codes. Considering these comparisons, Deuteronomy has come to be understood as a covenant, or treaty agreement between God and Israel, which sets out the terms and conditions of their relationship. The terms and conditions of this agreement include an emphasis on cult centralization, ritual purity laws, proper conduct of religious rituals, criminal laws, and social organization. Overall, the book of Deuteronomy establishes a contract between Israel and God whereby God’s presence will be guaranteed so long as Israel obeys the various terms and conditions of the contract.

Date Range: 700 BCE - 500 BCE

Region: Ancient Judah

Region tags: Eastern Mediterranean, Levant, Israel, Palestine

Ancient Judah at its greatest extent (South and West borders particularly flexible)

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Benjamin, Don, ed. *The Oxford Handbook of Deuteronomy*. Oxford University Press, 2020.
- Source 2: Coogan, Michael and Cynthia Chapman. *A Brief Introduction to the Old Testament: The*

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Inked

– with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Other textile: Parchment

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: Unknown

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: Unknown

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The versions of the Book of Deuteronomy at Qumran were stored in jars in caves. It is unknown if other manuscripts were stored in similar fashion.

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– I don't know

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– I don't know

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Field doesn't know

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– Yes

Notes: This text is considered official religious scripture by modern religious communities, but the notion of an "official religious scripture" is anachronistic to the communities who produced and first engaged with this text.

↳ Is there a culture of oral recitation?

– I don't know

↳ Is there a story associated with the origins of scripture?

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god?

– Yes

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being?

– No

↳ Inspired by high god?

– Yes

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being?

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings?

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being?

– Yes

Notes: Moses is also connected with the revelation of the second law in the Book of Deuteronomy.

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures?

– Yes

Notes: Scribes were likely responsible for the writing of "scripture" (again, anachronistic terminology). Scribes were trained to copy, alter, and compose texts.

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any specific gender designation?
– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any age designation?
– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any form of linguistic designation?
– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures?
– Field doesn't know

Notes: While the book of Deuteronomy is part of the Christian and Jewish canons, it was not part of any codified canon of scripture during the time of its initial production and consumption.

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Notes: Although Biblical Hebrew is now considered a religious or sacred language by certain communities, it likely reflected a language similar to the vernacular of the scribes and audiences of the text.

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Field doesn't know

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

Notes: There are slightly different versions of the book of Deuteronomy in the Masoretic Text, the Septuagint, and at Qumran. Ancient scribes and audiences would not have been bothered by variation.

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– No

Notes: As referenced above, the book of Deuteronomy was gathered into the collection of the Pentateuch but this would not have been considered "canonization."

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Field doesn't know

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: None

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– Yes

Are there formal institutions merged with the state or polity of the religious group?

– Field doesn't know

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites
– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world
– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
– No

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
– I don't know

↳ Knowledge is unrestrict outside of sample region
– I don't know

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
– Yes

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)
– Yes

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
– Yes

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- ↳ Has other knowledge of this world
 - Yes
- ↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
- ↳ Can reward
 - Yes
- ↳ Can punish
 - Yes
- ↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
- ↳ Exhibits positive emotion
 - Yes
- ↳ Exhibits negative emotion
 - Yes
- ↳ Possesses Hunger?
 - No
- ↳ Can be hurt?
 - No
- ↳ Can be tricked?
 - No
- ↳ Can be imprisoned?
 - No
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?
 - No

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life

– Yes

Notes: In Deuteronomy, only to a chosen prophet.

↳ In trance possession

– No

↳ Through divination practices

– No

Notes: See Deut 13 and 18. It is unlikely these restrictions reflect actual prophetic practices in ancient Israel.

↳ Only through religious specialists

– Yes

↳ Only through monarch

– No

Notes: See Deut 17.

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– I don't know

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Does the text guide divination practices?

– Yes

Notes: See Deut 13 and 18.

↳ Divination by examination of the extra (animal remains)

– No

↳ Divination through human communication?

– Yes

↳ Human being the vehicle for the oracle?

– Yes

↳ Human being the interpreter of the oracle?

– Yes

↳ Are the oracle interpreters of specified sex/gender?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the oracle interpreters of specified ethnicity?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the oracle interpreters of specified class?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is sex-deprivation required?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are intoxicants required?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is physical ordeal required?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Divination through animal-behavior?

– No

↳ Divination through non-living material?

–Other [specify]: No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– Yes

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– Yes

↳ Libations?

– Yes

↳ Food?

– Yes

↳ Animal sacrifice?

– Yes

↳ Human sacrifice?

– No

↳ Sacred objects?

– No

↳ Daily life objects?

– Yes

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos

– Yes

↳ Food
– Yes

↳ Sacred space(s)
– Yes

↳ Sacred object(s)
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions
– Yes

Notes: Deuteronomy demands the total destruction of other people groups in the region (See Deut 7). This seems to have both an ethnic and religious motivation.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities
– Yes

Notes: Deuteronomy demands the total destruction of other people groups in the region (See Deut 7). This seems to have both an ethnic and religious motivation.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex
– Yes

Notes: See Deut 22.

↳ Adultery
– Yes

↳ Incest
– Yes

↳ Taboo about close blood relations (beyond incest) [e.g. from same clan group, village, settlement, so forth].
– I don't know

↳ Specifies taboo regarding power relations (i.e. defines what constitutes abusive behavior)

– Yes

↳ Does worship/veneration include sex acts/references?

– No

↳ Other sexual practices

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?
– Yes

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?
– Yes

↳ Done only by high god
– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings
– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle
– No

↳ Done by other entities or through other means
– No

- ↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to enforce group norms?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?
 - I don't know
 - ↳ Done randomly
 - No
 - ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?
 - No
 - ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?
 - Yes
 - Notes: See Deut 28.
 - ↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Consists of bad luck?
 - No
 - ↳ Political failure?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Defeat in battle?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Crop failure or bad weather?
 - Yes

- ↳ Disaster on journeys?
– Yes
- ↳ Mild sensory displeasure?
– Yes
- ↳ Extreme sensory displeasure?
– Yes
- ↳ Sickness or illness?
– Yes
- ↳ Impaired reproduction?
– Yes
- ↳ Back luck visited on descendants?
– Yes

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

Notes: See Deut 7 and 28.

- ↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?
– Yes
 - ↳ Done only by high god
– Yes
 - ↳ Done by many supernatural beings
– No
 - ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle
– No
 - ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence
– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms?
– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?
– I don't know

↳ Done randomly
– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?
– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?
– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized?
– Yes

↳ Consists of good luck?
– No

↳ Consists of political success or power?
– Yes

↳ Consists of success in battle?
– Yes

↳ Consists of peace or social stability?
– Yes

↳ Consists of healthy crops or good weather?
– Yes

↳ Consists of success on journeys?
– Yes

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↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure?

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure?

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health?

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success?

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants?

– Yes

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

- ↳ Courage (in battle)
 - I don't know
- ↳ Courage (generic)
 - Yes
- ↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence
 - Yes
- ↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance
 - Yes
- ↳ Generosity/charity
 - Yes
- ↳ Selflessness/selfless giving
 - Yes
- ↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude
 - Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity
 - Yes
- ↳ Respectfulness/courtesy
 - Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience/filial piety
 - Yes
- ↳ Fidelity/loyalty
 - Yes
- ↳ Cooperation
 - Yes

- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
– No
- ↳ Moderation/frugality
– Yes
- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
– No
- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
– No
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
– No
- ↳ Strength (physical)
– No
- ↳ Power/status/nobility
– No
- ↳ Humility/modesty
– Yes
- ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
– No
- ↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
– No
- ↳ Optimism/hope
– No
- ↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
– Yes

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
– Yes

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
– Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding
– Yes

↳ Discernment/intelligence
– Yes

↳ Beauty/attractiveness
– No

– Yes

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
– Yes

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
– Yes

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
– Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding
– Yes

↳ Discernment/intelligence
– Yes

↳ Beauty/attractiveness
– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– Yes

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– Yes

Notes: Monogamy is not explicitly commanded, but a woman cannot sleep with more than one man and a man cannot sleep with a married woman or a virgin pledged or not yet pledged for marriage.

↳ Monogamy (males)

– No

↳ Monogamy (females)

– Yes

– Yes

Notes: Monogamy is not explicitly commanded, but a woman cannot sleep with more than one man and a man cannot sleep with a married woman or a virgin pledged or not yet pledged for marriage.

↳ Monogamy (males)

– No

↳ Monogamy (females)

– Yes

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– Yes

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– Yes

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– Yes

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Notes: Deuteronomy is more concerned with centralized worship than small scale worship.

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Yes

↳ On average, how many participants gather in one location?
– Field doesn't know

↳ Interval of time between performances (in hours)
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?
– Field doesn't know

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices?
– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there use of intoxicants?
– Field doesn't know

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?
– Field doesn't know

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?
– Yes

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?
– Field doesn't know

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?
– Yes

↳ Are sacrifices specified by the text?
– Yes

↳ Animal sacrifice?
– Yes

↳ Human sacrifice?

– No

↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

↳ Are there material offerings present?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the maintenance of the place regulated by the text?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A nation-state

Notes: This is a very complicated question, especially as we do not know under what political conditions the book of Deuteronomy was written and edited. It is likely that parts were written under the Judean polity/nation-state while other parts were written and compiled after the exile.

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: We cannot know what elements of society controlled the production or reproduction of the text. Control could have come from the monarchy, the temple institution, or particular scribal schools (or even a combination).

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: There is no evidence for the destruction of this text in antiquity.

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– Yes

Notes: See Deut 15. I wouldn't define this as "institutionalized" but the canceling of debts served to redistribute wealth across members of the community.

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– Yes

Notes: See Deut 14 and 18.

↳ Does the text require the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes?

– Yes

↳ Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question?

– No

↳ Is taxation linked to an understanding of charitable giving?

– Yes

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

↳ Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– No

↳ Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?
– I don't know

↳ Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?
– I don't know

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– Yes

↳ Does the text in question dictate how the religious group in question provide food for themselves?
– No

↳ Does the text celebrate/restrict food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question?
– No

↳ Which of the follow are forms of ritual food production [choose all that apply]?
– Pastoralism

Bibliography

General References

Reference: The Book of Deuteronomy, Quick, Laura. Deuteronomy 28 and the Aramaic Curse Tradition. Oxford University Press, 2017. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780198810933.001.0001>.

Reference: The Book of Deuteronomy, Crouch, Carly L., and Jeremy Michael Hutton. Translating Empire : Tell Fekheriyeh, Deuteronomy, and the Akkadian Treaty Tradition. Forschungen Zum Alten Testament 135. Tübingen: Mohr Siebeck, 2019.

Reference: The Book of Deuteronomy, Baden, Joel S., and Jeffrey Stackert, eds.. The Oxford Handbook of the Pentateuch. Edited by Joel S. Baden and Jeffrey Stackert. Oxford University Press, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780198726302.001.0001>.

Reference: The Book of Deuteronomy, Benjamin, Don, ed.. The Oxford Handbook of Deuteronomy. Edited by Don Benjamin. Oxford University Press, 2020. <https://doi-org.proxy1.library.jhu.edu/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780190273552.001.0001>.